

DataTools4Heart

A European Health Data Toolbox for Enhancing Cardiology Data Interoperability, Reusability and Privacy

Milestone MS15:

AI-powered Virtual Assistants (VAs) supporting multilingual interaction in at least 7 languages built, demonstrated, and released

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Version Log

Issue Date	Version	Involved	Comments
17/03/2026	V0.1	Chara Tsoukala (ATH)	Initial draft
27/03/2026	Final	Karim Lekadir, Cristian Izquierdo, Xènia Puig (UB)	Revised and corrected final version

Executive Summary

MS15 has been achieved. The DataTools4Heart (DT4H) Virtual Assistant has been integrated into the DT4H platform, demonstrated to relevant stakeholder groups, and released as an operational component supporting multilingual interaction in seven languages: English, Spanish, Swedish, Dutch, Italian, Romanian, and Czech. The VA enables natural-language access to the Data Catalogue and supports privacy-preserving retrieval of aggregated cohort metadata through FEM/SMPC, while operating within the platform's secure authentication and access-control framework. The milestone outcome was validated through repeated demonstrations to clinicians, researchers, AI developers, technical partners, and ethics/legal experts during consortium meetings. MS15 is further evidenced by Deliverable D6.1, which provides demonstrator material for the platform and the AI-powered Virtual Assistant.

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Acronyms

DT4H: DataTools4Heart

FEM: Federated Execution Manager

SMPC: Secure Multi-party Computation

VA: Virtual Assistant

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1 MS15 Objective

MS15 required the DataTools4Heart Virtual Assistant (VA) to be built, integrated into the platform, demonstrated to relevant stakeholders, and released with multilingual interaction in at least seven languages.

2 Status and results achieved

The DT4H Virtual Assistant is available as an operational component of the DT4H platform and is also accessible through the dedicated entry point at <https://chomsky.i1sp.gr/dt4h>. It is integrated with the common DT4H authentication and access-control layer based on Keycloak (Figure 1), providing secure and role-based access across platform services. This integration ensures that users authenticate only once, while permissions are propagated consistently across the different services involved in study and dataset discovery and metadata querying.

From a user perspective, the VA supports a structured workflow for exploring sensitive healthcare data. Users can start a new conversation, select one of the supported languages, consult the [user documentation](#) directly from the interface, and navigate previous chats through the conversation-history panel. Each chat thread is stored with a title and timestamp and can be copied to the clipboard, exported in Microsoft Word format, or deleted at thread level (Figure 2). These functions improve traceability and reproducibility and are particularly useful for researchers and clinicians who need to keep a record of specific questions, share responses with collaborators, or archive discussion outputs for later review.

The VA supports multilingual interaction in seven languages: English, Spanish, Swedish, Dutch, Italian, Romanian, and Czech (Figure 5). Multilingual support is implemented not only at the user interface level, but also in the prompting and orchestration logic of the assistant. In practice, users can formulate requests in their preferred language, and the assistant can interpret these requests, plan the required actions, and return responses in the same language. This is particularly important in the DT4H setting, where users may come from different countries. Initial testing indicates that the multilingual workflow remains functional across the supported languages (see for instance Figure 4 for a user flow in Spanish), including for requests involving study discovery, cohort inspection, and metadata retrieval.

The end-to-end user interaction flow is as follows: Users can first search the Data Catalogue in natural language to identify relevant studies, cohorts, datasets, variables, and contributing nodes. They can ask targeted questions such as which datasets include particular clinical features, which hospitals contribute to a given cohort, or whether a certain variable is available across selected nodes (see Figure 3 for an example user flow). When the user asks for cohort-level statistics, the assistant checks whether the requested metadata are already available for the selected study and nodes. If not, the assistant guides the user to create a new metadata request (Figure 6), where the study and participating nodes are specified before submission. Once the request is launched, the VA coordinates the interaction with the FEM/SMPC infrastructure and returns only aggregated outputs, such as counts, ranges, or other summary metadata. No identifiable or row-level data leave the hospital nodes.

Because metadata requests are executed through distributed secure multi-party computation, the processing time may be several minutes depending on the number of participating nodes and the requested aggregation. To preserve a smooth conversational experience, the VA is designed so that users can define the required study and nodes in advance through the request workflow and then continue the conversation once the aggregated results are available. This avoids the need to restart the analysis path and allows users to move naturally from data discovery, to metadata request creation, to interpretation of the returned results within the same conversational context.

2.1 Demonstration to stakeholders

In DT4H, the stakeholders include clinicians, clinical researchers, AI developers, technical partners, and ethics/legal experts. This requirement was fulfilled through repeated demonstrations of the VA at consortium meetings, where the system was presented to these stakeholder groups and discussed in relation to use cases, usability, privacy-preserving access to metadata, and platform integration.

2.2 Link to Deliverable 6.1

MS15 is also linked to D6.1 “Platform global infrastructure and AI-powered Virtual Assistants”, due on the same date. D6.1 is a demonstration deliverable consisting of a video demo of the platform and VA together with a short supporting document with screenshots. It provides demonstrator evidence for the released platform and VA.

3 Conclusion

MS15 is considered achieved. The DT4H Virtual Assistant has been built, integrated into the platform, released, and demonstrated to relevant stakeholders. It supports multilingual interaction in seven languages and provides operational support for dataset exploration and privacy-preserving cohort metadata retrieval within the DT4H platform.

Figure 1: Integration with centralised authentication hosted by BSC.

Figure 2: Option to copy, export, or delete chat thread.

Figure 3: User flow of the VA interface, showing how users access and interact with sensitive healthcare data through the Data Catalogue, and FEM client/SMPC integration.

Español ▼ Logout

 ¡Bienvenido! Soy un asistente inteligente para investigadores clínicos en cardiología. Puedo asistirte con las siguientes tareas:

1. **Explorar el Catálogo de Datos (DC):** Selecciona una cohorte basada en características específicas de los pacientes o variables incluidas en los estudios.
2. **Obtener estadísticas:** Accede a estadísticas clave del conjunto de datos seleccionado, que pueden ayudarte a evaluar su elegibilidad y explorar su contenido.
3. **Visualización de datos:** Visualiza el conjunto de datos para obtener mejores perspectivas y análisis.

Para comenzar, exploremos el Catálogo de Datos. ¿Qué características específicas de los pacientes o variables te interesan para la selección de la cohorte? También puedes solicitar una lista con todos los nombres de cohortes disponibles en el DC.

¿Cuáles son las cohortes disponibles?

 Las cohortes disponibles son:

1. **Study1**
 - Número de características: 401
 - Nodos disponibles: AUMC, GEM, ICRC, RS, UCLH, UMCU
2. **maggic**
 - Número de características: 25
 - Nodos disponibles: maggic_codebook

¿Hay algún estudio que incluya pacientes con ERC que también hayan sido diagnosticados de hiperpotasemia?

 Sí, el estudio que incluye pacientes con enfermedad renal crónica (ERC) y que también han sido diagnosticados de hiperpotasemia es **Study1**.

Quiero explorar este estudio. ¿Cuál es la gravedad de la ERC?

 La gravedad de la enfermedad renal crónica (ERC) en el estudio **Study1** se categoriza de la siguiente manera:

- Leve: 2 pacientes
- Moderada: 7 pacientes
- Normal: 3 pacientes

Figure 4: User flow in Spanish.

Figure 5: Language selection for the consortium languages.

Figure 6: Screen to request aggregated metadata through SMPC.